

HOW CAN MULTIMODAL DEEP LEARNING DETECT VIOLENCE IN LOW-RESOURCE SINHALA SOCIAL MEDIA POSTS?

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ABSTRACT

Social media is an integral aspect of daily life, yet it also serves as an avenue for disseminating violent content. Image-based posts, in particular, serve as powerful vehicles for such content, prompting efforts to automatically detect and combat this issue. While studies predominantly focus on English content, fewer explore languages with limited digital resources, such as Sinhala. Our research pioneers the classification of Sinhala image posts based on both textual and visual features and introduced a foundational work in the context of a low resource language, Sinhala by adapting standard models for this underexplored domain. As the first step, we introduced a new annotated dataset of Sinhala image posts, with extracted textual and visual components. Furthermore, we employed a customized Tesseract OCR and the EAST library for automatic extraction of these components. After pre-processing the textual data, we utilized models, including LSTM, GRU, 1D CNN, and ensemble models combining 1D CNN with GRU, LSTM, BiGRU, and BiLSTM, alongside word2vec embeddings. Additionally, we incorporated XLM-R, a multilingual transformer-based model, to enhance textual classification. For visual analysis, pre-trained models such as ResNet, AlexNet, ViT, and EfficientNet were employed. Finally, we employed an SVM-based late fusion multimodal model for classification. Our approach achieved 95% accuracy, surpassing single-modality results. This marks significant progress in addressing violent content in Sinhala image posts on social media. Although architecture employs standard models, adopting these models to Sinhala language and the creation of a baseline dataset marks a significant contribution.

Keywords: *Deep Learning, Multimodal, NLP, Social Media, Violence*

1. INTRODUCTION

Social media is a platform that generates a variety of content, which can be in the form of text, images, or videos. However, either intentionally or unintentionally, the content created can be violent or non-violent. Over time, such violent content can lead to physical violence or cause emotional harm in society. As a result, certain content on social media negatively impacts society. Among the different forms of content, image posts play a significant role in disseminating information—whether that information is violent or non-violent. Although an image post can convey non-violent information, the majority of posts tend to subtly attack race, ethnicity, politics, and religion. Given that these posts encompass both textual and visual elements, they can reach a wider

audience compared to those containing only text or visuals.

The classification of social media content as violent or non-violent is of paramount importance, as it enables us to safeguard the entire community from physical or emotional harm. To classify image posts, we need to consider both visual and textual elements. We refer to these elements as visual and textual features, respectively.

1.1 Social Media and Image Posts: A Global Perspective

Social media usage increased significantly in 2025. According to the data, 63.9% of the world's total population uses social media [1]. In 2025, social

media usage shows a 4.1% increase compared to 2024. This study has also revealed that the average duration of a person spending on social media exceeds 2 hours per day. Based on the results, Facebook, YouTube, WhatsApp, and Instagram are the most used social media channels. Within these channels, image posts are a popular discourse mechanism. With the growing popularity of image posts, a study has revealed that memes, which are image posts, may become a part of an evolving digital language as the younger generation has a greater tendency towards using memes [2]. A recent study related to the war in Ukraine [3] has emerged, showing how memes, which are image posts with visual and textual content, disseminate hateful content to dehumanize specific parties. One of the first studies presented several incidents in Bangladesh [4], where the roots of the violence originated on social networks. The misuse of Facebook and the spread of fake news have contributed to these incidents in Bangladesh. Another incident was related to immigrants in Italy [5], where images that included violence were generated on a social media site. These incidents show how social media can generate violence that may later result in physical harm.

1.2 Social Media and Image Posts in Sri Lanka

Most studies related to image posts focus on the English language. However, in this research, our primary focus is on Sinhala, which is the native language of Sinhalese people, who are the largest ethnic group in Sri Lanka, which is a low-resource language in the context of Natural Language Processing (NLP) and Machine Learning (ML). In this context, a low-resource language refers to a language with limited digital resources and available data for training NLP or ML models. More than 35% of the population in Sri Lanka use social media [6]. Facebook and YouTube are the most frequently used social media sites. Historically, image posts have played a significant role in public discourse in Sri Lanka related to political shifts, mass casualty attacks—including the Easter attack and economic crisis that led to widespread protests [7]. In these instances, image posts related to these incidents were shared extensively on social media.

1.3 Research Aim, Questions, and Objectives

This research proposes a model for predicting whether a social media image post in the context of the Sinhala language is violent or non-

violent. Additionally, the objective of this study is to separate the text and image features of image posts and train machine learning models independently for each of these features. The violence score will represent the overall violence level between the text and image features to determine whether a post is classified as violent or non-violent.

Research Question 1 (RQ1): Does a dataset currently exist that includes Sinhala image posts containing both textual and visual elements?

Objective 1: Develop an annotated dataset that encompasses both violent and non-violent images, while incorporating both textual and visual features.

Research Question 2 (RQ2): What methodologies can be employed to separately extract visual and text features?

Objective 2: Investigate the available techniques for feature extraction in the context of both visual and textual features. Identify available OCR technologies, that can be used for the extraction.

Research Question 3 (RQ3): How can textual content of an image post be categorized as violent or non-violent?

Objective 3: Utilize current state-of-the-art natural language processing and machine learning algorithms to extract features from textual content and classify it into categories of violent or non-violent content.

Research Question 4 (RQ4): How can visual features of an image post be classified as violent or non-violent?

Objective 4: Apply existing machine learning and deep learning models for image classification and adapt them to our specific task through fine-tuning.

Research Question 5 (RQ5): How can an image post containing both textual and visual components be classified as violent or non-violent?

Objective 5: Develop a hybrid method to integrate results from textual and visual classification to classify an image post as violent or non-violent.

1.4 Contribution and Novelty

This research introduces the first foundational attempt to apply multimodal learning for

violence detection in Sinhala-language social media posts. The primary contribution is the creation of a novel multimodal dataset, including image posts, their corresponding textual components (extracted from embedded text), and visual components separately for Sinhala language. Additionally, we implemented a mechanism to extract textual part of a post automatically using an existing OCR. Subsequently, a mechanism was developed for visual extraction. We have also trained and evaluated standard models, including convolutional neural networks (CNNs), long short-term memory (LSTM), Gated Recurrent Unit (GRU), and further explored ensemble models that combine standard models. In addition, we fine-tuned existing pre-trained models for textual and visual classification tasks. To optimize model performance, we employed GridSearch mechanism for identifying optimal hyperparameters. Finally, we developed a multimodal classification model using late fusion for image posts classification. While architectural techniques such as LSTM, CNN, GRU, and late fusion are existing standard models, adapting and evaluating these models to introduce a multimodal model for the Sinhala language constitute a significant and original contribution of this research.

In light of recent studies that use multimodal learning to detect hate speech and violence—primarily in English and other well-resourced languages—we make the following contributions, categorized as follows:

Dataset Contribution:

We introduced a novel multimodal dataset for Sinhala, consisting of the following three components:

- The main component of the dataset comprises annotated image posts categorized as violent and non-violent.
- Extracted textual content (both manually and using OCR).
- Extracted visual content.

This is a significant contribution to the field of multimodal data analysis, as none of the existing studies have presented a multimodal dataset with independently extracted textual and visual components. This finding is not only important for Sinhala but also holds relevance for English.

Methodological Contribution:

In the multimodal analysis pipeline, we also utilized a customized OCR technique to automatically extract text, a method that is rarely used in other studies. Most existing studies in the multimodal context do not extract the visual component separately; however, in this study, we have explicitly extracted the visual component as an independent modality.

Additionally, we employed a customized GridSearch method for hyperparameter tuning, which has not been commonly used in most multimodal-related studies.

Multimodal Fusion:

As the main contribution, we have presented a late fusion multimodal technique for classifying Sinhala image posts, which is a novel outcome for the Sinhala language.

1.5 Outline of the Paper

For the reader's convenience, we have organized the paper as follows: The Related Work section discusses research studies relevant to our work. Subsequently, the Materials and Methods section outlines the materials and methodologies employed in our research. The Results and Discussion section presents and analyzes the results of our study. The Significance of the Proposed Approach chapter compares our study in the context of state-of-the-art research presented in the literature. Finally, the Conclusion section provides insights drawn from our study.

2. RELATED WORK

This chapter attempts to explore the presence of violence across different media formats, either text-based, image-based, or some combination of these modalities. Furthermore, the methods used to identify violence can take the form of simple ML approaches or complex deep learning (DL) methods.

2.1 Violence Detection in Text

Textual elements classification on social media for violence detection primarily focuses on hate speech. Initially rule-based feature extraction

was used in this context. Ellen Spertus developed a system, "Smokey," to detect hostile messages in 1992 as the earliest work in this area to our knowledge [8]. The author used private messages sent through feedback forms from different websites: controversial websites were used as the dataset. The research consisted of a natural language processor and a rule-based parser to build a feature vector; a decision tree-based approach was used to classify the text as 'okay,' 'maybe,' or 'flame.' The system was able to classify 98% of 'okay' and 64% of 'flame' correctly. Limitations in the study included difficulties in classifying sarcasm, complex sentences, and sentences with mistakes in grammar and punctuation, etc. In 2008, authors implemented a similar system using a rule-based approach. Unlike *Smokey*, which primarily relies on pattern matching, the new approach proposed by Mahmud et al. [9] is based on a general semantic structure that extracts semantic meaning. While 'Smokey' is message level, the method proposed by Mahmud et al. [9] is sentence-level. One of the limitations in the research proposed by Mahmud et al. is that the words should be in the lexicon entry to be identified as hate speech. One significant drawback of the rule-based approach is its reliance on a dictionary. The methodology is heavily dependent on having a large dictionary to analyze contextual words. As a result, researchers have explored alternative approaches, such as Bag-of-Words (BoW), where the method constructs a dictionary based on the training dataset.

Due to the limitations of rule-based approaches, hate text detection methods have employed techniques such as unigram, bigram, n-gram, term frequency - inverse document frequency (TF-IDF), character n-gram, and word2vec.

Most research studies on hate in textual content, using BoW, TF-IDF, and other feature extraction methods, focus on analyzing tweets. Although data plays a paramount role in any machine learning task, including hate speech detection, there is a lack of large, publicly available datasets. To address this gap, Waseem and Hovy curated a dataset of tweets annotated with labels such as racism, sexism, and none for hate speech detection [10]. Their findings revealed that using character n-grams with logistic regression (LR) as the classification algorithm produced better results than word n-grams [10].

Davidson et al. employed shallow learning algorithms, such as support vector machines (SVM), naïve Bayes (NB), LR, decision trees (DTs), and random forest (RF), combined with feature extraction methods like unigrams, bigrams, and trigrams weighted with TF-IDF for hate speech detection in tweets [11]. Among these methods, LR outperformed the other algorithms in this research [11].

Malmasi and Zampieri [12] employed the dataset created by Davidson et al. in a previous study [11]. Character n-grams, word n-grams, and skip-grams were applied as feature extraction methods to detect hate speech. Among these methods, character 4-gram method showed better results than the others, achieving an accuracy of 78%. Nonetheless, this study did not utilize BoW models weighted TF-IDF, which, according to research conducted by Davidson et al. [11], have demonstrated superior performance. When comparing the confusion matrices of two studies conducted on the same dataset, it is evident that the research by Malmasi and Zampieri [12] misclassified more than 50% of hate tweets as offensive or neither. Moreover, the percentage of misclassification in the offensive category was also higher compared to the results reported by Davidson et al. [11]. This comparison suggests that the model employed by Davidson et al. [11] outperforms the model proposed by Malmasi and Zampieri [12].

Gaydhani et al. utilized NB, LR, and SVM with TF-IDF weighted n-gram features alongside L2 and L1 regularization for hate speech classification [13]. The authors used three datasets from various sources, including [14], the dataset from Davidson et al. [11], and the dataset created by Waseem and Hovy [10]. Since the dataset created by Waseem and Hovy [10] includes classes such as racism, sexism, and none, both the racism and sexism classes were considered forms of hate. NB and LR produced comparable results with L2 regularization. Furthermore, Gaydhani et al. found that results could be further improved by using TF-IDF weighted n-gram features. Both Davidson et al. [11] and Gaydhani et al. [13] discovered that using LR with L2 regularization in combination with TF-IDF weighted n-gram features yielded superior results in detecting hate speech in tweets. Moreover, their findings demonstrate enhanced accuracy in hate text identification, as reflected in the confusion matrix. Additionally, this study [13] showed significant improvements in F1-score, precision, and recall

compared to the results reported by Waseem and Hovy [10].

Another comparative study that utilized bigram with TF-IDF, word2vec, and doc2vec as features, along with classification algorithms such as LR, NB, RF, SVM, k-nearest neighbor (KNN), DT, AdaBoost, and Multilayer Perceptron (MLP), reported higher accuracy using SVM with bigram compared to other feature extraction methods for hate speech detection on tweets [15]. The authors used a publicly available dataset from CrowdFlower [14]. However, the study also demonstrated comparable results for LR, which aligns with the findings of Davidson et al. [11] and Gaydhani et al. [13].

Badjatiya et al. [16] investigated hate speech detection in tweets by employing both shallow machine learning (ML) methods and DL algorithms. The shallow ML algorithms included SVM and LR, combined with BoW and TF-IDF. The DL algorithms included CNNs, LSTM, and fastText as feature representations. The study revealed that DL performed better than ML models.

Gambäck and Sikdar employed CNN to classify tweets as racism, sexism, both (racism and sexism), and non-hate-speech, using four feature extraction methods: random vectors, word2vec, character n-grams, and a combination of word2vec with character n-grams [17]. The Twitter dataset created by Waseem and Hovy [10] served as the basis for this study. Higher precision was achieved with random vectors, whereas higher recall and F1-score were obtained with word2vec. The random embedding-based CNN approach demonstrated superior results compared to the baseline method proposed by Waseem and Hovy [10]. Moreover, employing GBDT further improved the results. However, the method introduced by Badjatiya et al. [16] outperformed the CNN-based approach from Gambäck and Sikdar's study [17]. In particular, Badjatiya et al. demonstrated that LSTM models consistently outperformed CNN-based methods in detecting hate speech. Both studies—Gambäck and Sikdar [17] and Badjatiya et al. [16]—concluded that random embeddings tend to yield better performance than other embedding mechanisms, particularly in tasks related to hate speech detection.

A study was conducted to detect abusive language on Twitter using Character-level Convolutional Neural Network (charCNN), Word-level Convolutional Neural Network (wordCNN),

and Hybrid Convolutional Neural Network (HybridCNN) [18]. The authors utilized the same dataset as the two previous deep learning studies by Gambäck and Sikdar [17] and Badjatiya et al. [16], both of which were based on the dataset created by Waseem and Hovy [10]. In the charCNN model, each character in the input sentence was converted to a one-hot encoding, which was then fed into the CNN model. In the wordCNN model, words were embedded using word2vec embeddings. The HybridCNN model combined both the wordCNN and charCNN models. The classification process included both one-step and two-step approaches. For the one-step classification, the classes considered were none, racist, and sexist. In the two-step method, the initial classification differentiated between abusive and non-abusive classes, followed by a subsequent classification of the abusive class into racist and sexist categories. Baseline methods included LR [10], SVM, and fastText. The two-step approach using HybridCNN with LR achieved superior performance compared to other methods. However, it did not surpass the method utilizing random embeddings, LSTM with GBDT in a previous study on the same dataset [16].

In 2018, Zhang et al. developed a Twitter dataset focusing on conversations about refugees and Muslims to detect hate speech [19]. They implemented an ensemble model that combined CNN and GRU using both random and pre-trained embeddings. One key challenge with pre-trained embeddings was handling out-of-vocabulary (OOV) words. To address this, the researchers either assigned random vectors using a uniform distribution or used the vector of a randomly selected in-vocabulary word. The researchers evaluated their model on seven datasets, including their own, and found that it outperformed the SVM-based model developed by Davidson et al. [11] when applied to the dataset created by Zhang et al. [19]. Additionally, it exceeded the performance of the LSTM and GBDT model created by Badjatiya et al. [16] on the dataset created by Davidson et al. [11]. However, it did not achieve better results when tested on a larger dataset created by Waseem and Hovy [10].

Another study [20] on hate speech detection in Twitter focused on improving the accuracy of detecting non-hate content compared to hate speech using DL algorithms, including CNN and Gated Recurrent Unit (GRU). The CNNs included

traditional CNNs along with modified CNN layers that act as skip-gram extractors, called “skip-CNN”.

Furthermore, large language models like Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transform (BERT)-based transfer learning methods have been applied to hate speech identification on Twitter. One such study demonstrated that using BERT for Twitter data classification has yielded better results than state-of-the-art methods such as LR [21]. Additionally, two other research studies on hate speech detection in Twitter found that BERT-based methods outperformed other DL and shallow learning methods [22], [23].

Although most of the above research studies focused on tweets, some utilized a dataset created by Conversation AI, led by Jigsaw and Google, which is available on Kaggle [24], as well as a dataset based on Facebook comments [25]. The Kaggle dataset includes Wikipedia comments, while the dataset created by Kumar et al. contains aggression-annotated Facebook posts and comments in both Hindi and English languages [25].

Srivastava et al. conducted a study to recognize toxic and aggressive text using a dataset created by Conversation AI [24] and a dataset composed of Facebook comments [25]. Their approach employed a capsule network with focal loss [26], [27], [28]. The proposed capsule network outperformed methods involving LSTM and CNN architectures. These results were compared with the original study conducted by Kumar et al. [25], which used a combination of Bidirectional LSTM (BiLSTM) and attention mechanisms. Notably, the results obtained by the capsule network exceeded those reported in the original paper [25].

In another study using the Toxic Comment Classification Challenge dataset [24], four embedding mechanisms were investigated within an attention-ensemble model. The text embedding mechanisms included GloVe, fastText, a method that concatenated the embeddings of GloVe and fastText, and a reverse-concatenated approach that reversed the order of GloVe and fastText embeddings. Although attention mechanisms alone do not capture all the information in a sequence, they become powerful when combined with features such as positional encoding, which helps reduce complexity and memory requirements. The proposed model outperformed the Bidirectional Gated Recurrent Unit (BiGRU) model [29];

however, it did not surpass the performance of the previous study that applied capsule networks to the same dataset [28].

In another study, the authors proposed an ensemble method that combines a fine-tuned BERT-based model with a parallel recurrent model for multi-aspect hate speech detection [23]. The model was trained and tested on a dataset created by Conversation AI, led by Jigsaw and Google [24]. The proposed model was compared to pooled stacked BiLSTM and BiGRU models, as well as ensemble models that combined the outputs of BERT, BiLSTM, and BiGRU. Among individual models, the pre-trained BERT model demonstrated a higher AUC than other deep learning models, highlighting the effectiveness of transformer-based models, even with an imbalanced dataset. The results improved when the BERT model was integrated with other deep learning models. The BERT model also showed better F1 scores but lower precision for most of the labels considered. In contrast, models associated with LSTM and GRU demonstrated higher precision for most labels but lower recall. However, the effectiveness of ensemble-based models over individual classifiers was primarily observed for majority labels such as 'toxic,' 'insult,' and 'obscene.' Interestingly, for minority labels like 'severe toxic,' 'threat,' and 'identity hate,' the ensemble-based models did not yield improvements in Recall, Precision, or F1 score. Overall, the new model outperformed those proposed by Srivastava et al. for the same dataset [28].

Racist or hate speech classification in Sinhala has been conducted using shallow algorithms [30], [31], [32], such as SVM and Multinomial NB (MNB), along with TF-IDF and n-gram methods. Both MNB and SVM demonstrated higher results than other methods. In one of the earliest works addressing Sinhala, researchers identified racist Sinhala comments using a two-class SVM and an n-gram approach with TF-IDF as the weighting function, achieving over 70% accuracy [30]. As a first step, the authors constructed a dataset comprised of randomly selected Sinhala comments from social media platforms. However, the performance of the model declined as the dataset size expanded due to the imbalanced nature of the dataset. Notably, false negatives increased despite the addition of more positive data, while false positives remained at zero.

Sandaruwan et al. conducted a study to identify abusive comments in the Sinhala language

[31]. The authors developed a dataset using social media platforms such as YouTube, Facebook, and gossip sites. They analyzed the dataset and applied pre-processing techniques, including stop word removal and stemming. The authors employed SVM, MNB, and Random Forest Decision Tree (RFDT) as classifiers. For feature extraction, BoW, word n-gram, character n-gram, and word skip-gram were used. MNB outperformed the other classifiers, and character trigrams and four-grams produced better results than other feature extraction methods. While both studies by Ruwandika and Weerasinghe [33] and Dias et al. [30] experimented with TF-IDF related feature extraction, Sandaruwan et al. found that character n-grams were a more effective approach for hate classification.

For the first time in the Sinhala language, hate speech in images was classified based on text extracted from images [32]. However, this research focused solely on the textual component and did not incorporate image features. The text was automatically extracted from images, and only images with a white background, free of complex elements, were considered. For classification, several shallow machine learning models, such as KNN, SVC, LR, MNB, and RF, were utilized. Among the models tested, MNB outperformed the others in terms of precision, recall, and F-measure. In previous studies, MNB has also demonstrated superior performance, as noted by Sandaruwan et al. [31].

However, due to the challenges associated with Sinhala as a low-resource language, the authors encountered difficulties in obtaining an appropriate dataset. More recently, techniques like BERT and Cross-Lingual Language Model with RoBERTa (XLM-R) architecture [34], [35] have also been experimented for Sinhala text classification, and they outperformed other shallow and DL models.

Adapter-based pre-trained multilingual models were proposed for code-mixed and code-switched text classification, including Sinhala text [34]. Rathnayake et al. constructed a new dataset using the dataset created by Chathuranga and Ranathunga [36]. The cross-lingual representation of robustly optimized BERT pre-training (XLM-R), with basic fine-tuning, outperformed all other models, including the capsule network proposed by Senevirathne et al. [37], LSTM, and BiLSTM networks. Moreover, XLM-R with adapters further improved the results.

"BERTifying Sinhala" is an analysis conducted to evaluate the performance of transformer-based models, including XLM-R, Language-Agnostic BERT Sentence Embedding (LaBSE), and Language-Agnostic Sentence Representations (LASER), in Sinhala text classification [35]. In this study, XLM-R outperformed the other models. Both the studies by Rathnayake et al [34]. and Dhananjaya et al. [35] demonstrated that XLM-R is a superior model for text classification.

2.2 Violence detection in Images

Research on visual element classification has primarily focused on violent image classification. One such study examined violent image detection in a protest image dataset and employed a residual network (ResNet)-based architecture [38]. ResNet achieved strong performance on this dataset. Another study utilized multi-view maximum cross-entropy discrimination [39]. This approach incorporates low-level features such as dense scale-invariant feature transform (DSIFT), histogram of oriented gradient (HOG), and local binary pattern (LBP) to classify violent and non-violent images. The dataset is composed of still images collected from online search engines, such as Google and screenshots from movies. The proposed method outperformed state-of-the-art single-view and multi-view approaches.

2.3 Violence detection in Multimodal Data

In the context of this research, the primary focus is on classifying textual and visual modalities for violence detection. Therefore, in a multimodal approach, the input consists of both textual and visual elements, and feature extraction is performed separately for each modality. To combine different modalities, various fusion methods, such as early fusion and late fusion, are used.

Gang violence refers to violent activities committed by a group of people. A multimodal approach was employed to detect gang violence [40] in an image dataset collected from Twitter. For the textual features, unigram, bigram, Part-of-Speech (PoS) tagging, and CNN were used. Visual features were detected using a Regional-based convolutional neural network (R-CNN). In this research fusion methods used to combine results from both textual and visual elements demonstrated promising results. Another study that utilized tweets, examined three

components of a tweet: the image, the text inside the image and the text outside the image, which were used as inputs to the model. Considering all three elements of a tweet, both unimodal and multimodal models were tested to classify hate speech in memes [41]. According to the authors, the multimodal approach did not outperform the textual models. Furthermore, another study created a dataset of social media memes to apply multimodal approaches for classifying offensive memes [42]. The dataset was collected from social media platforms such as Reddit, Facebook, Twitter, and Instagram. LSTM, BiLSTM, and CNN were used to extract text features, while Visual Geometry Group (VGG-16) was used to extract visual features. The multimodal approach outperformed the unimodal models.

Facebook AI conducted a Hateful Meme Challenge [43] to classify hateful memes. They created a dataset by generating a new set of memes that represented those found in the wild, that is, actual memes found on Facebook. The text was pre-extracted during the annotation process, allowing researchers to use the text separately and eliminating the need for optical character recognition (OCR). Different fusion techniques were used to combine the features from different modalities. Among them, the multimodal approach using early fusion yielded superior results. Kirk et al. [44] evaluated the method proposed by Facebook AI using real memes collected from Pinterest and used three popular OCR tools, including Tesseract [45], to extract text. Their findings indicated that the synthetic dataset created by Facebook AI overestimated performance when compared to a dataset of real memes.

A research study aimed at detecting harmful Covid-19 related memes [46] employed Google's Vision OCR API to automatically extract text from memes. They compared unimodal models which utilize only textual or visual data, with multimodal models. DL models such as BERT were used for the text elements while pre-trained models such as ResNet, VGG19, and DenseNet were employed for visual elements. Multimodal approaches that combined outputs from unimodal models, as well as multimodal techniques involving pre-trained multimodal models such as Supervised Multimodal Bitransformers (MMBT) [47] and Vision and Language BERT (ViLBERT) [48], were used to compare the results. The approaches that utilized pre-trained multimodal models yielded superior results.

Another multimodal research study [49] was conducted to detect fake news using a popular dataset consisting of images collected from Reddit and other social news and discussion platforms. A fine-tuned BERT model was used for the textual features, while a fine-tuned Xception network [50] was used for the visual features. The multimodal approach yielded superior results compared to models that used only text or visual data. Table 1 depicts a summary of the studies described in the related work section.

2.4 Research Gap

According to the literature we studied, there is currently no publicly available image post dataset that includes both textual and visual components separately for English as well as for Sinhala. Since our study focuses on Sinhala, we have introduced a novel dataset, that includes both textual and visual components separately, along with the corresponding image posts. In most of the available studies, textual content is manually extracted, and visual content is not extracted as a separate modality. However, in our study, we have tested our models with both manually as well as automatically extracted text. Additionally, we have separated the visual components and classified them independently. As of the date of publishing this paper, we have not identified any other study related to multimodal data analysis for the Sinhala language. Therefore, this work is the first of its kind in the context of the Sinhala language.

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

This section outlines the step-by-step approach we have taken to classify Sinhala image posts as violent or non-violent based on their textual and visual features. Our literature review has highlighted challenges in obtaining a suitable dataset and extracting text from these posts. Figure 1 illustrates the process involved in training the textual and visual components of image posts. This process ensures that both modalities are effectively learned before integrating them into the multimodal model for classification.

3.1 Research Method Protocol Overview

To identify an image post as violent or non-violent, we developed a multimodal deep learning pipeline consisting of six main stages as follows.

Dataset Preparation: A new balanced dataset consisting of 4,500 image posts was curated. The dataset was sourced from Facebook and utilized a keyword search-based manual method to collect violent and non-violent image posts. Native Sinhala speakers were involved in the dataset annotation process.

Text Extraction: First text extraction was manually conducted. Then a customized text extraction pipeline using Tesseract OCR was utilized for automatic text extraction. The OCR process was enhanced using image pre-processing, Sinhala font training, post-processing using a Sinhala dictionary, and a custom word-level accuracy evaluation technique.

Visual Extraction: Visual content was extracted by removing the detected text regions (using Tesseract OCR). A mask was applied to retain only the visual components for classification.

Text Classification: Cleaned and pre-processed text was classified using deep learning models such as 1D CNN, LSTM, GRU, and a fine-tuned XLM-R transformer. Hyperparameter tuning was performed using GridSearchCV and manual tuning for large models.

Visual Classification: Several pre-trained image classification models were used for visual classification.

Multimodal Fusion: A late fusion strategy was involved using traditional ML models such as SVM to integrate both visual and text classification results.

The following section provides a detailed description of the research methodology protocol.

3.2 Dataset Preparation

We have introduced a new balanced dataset consisting of violent and non-violent image posts, which addresses the research gap related to the lack of available multimodal datasets with both textual and visual extracted components. The dataset will be made publicly available to support further research, enabling the academic community to utilize, validate, and extend it for related tasks. Many existing datasets contain image posts with low resolution, complex backgrounds, and varying font formats, which hinder the effectiveness of OCR techniques in extracting textual parts [50], [51].

This, in turn, makes it difficult to extract visual components as well. Nevertheless, our new dataset is balanced, containing an equal number of violent and non-violent image posts, whereas some existing datasets suffer from data imbalance due to the scarcity of violent image posts [50].

3.2.1 Data Collection

Initially we evaluated various social media platforms and chose Facebook as our primary data source, as the majority of Sinhala image posts are found there. The collection focused on two categories: violent and non-violent posts. Non-violent posts included topics such as love, knowledge, parenting techniques, cricket, quotes, religion, and politics, while violent posts included content related to sexism, fights, violence, and conveyed offensive or aggressive sentiments. To gather non-violent posts, we primarily collected data from pages dedicated to themes like love, parenting, knowledge, and quotes. However, we found fewer Facebook pages specifically dedicated to violent images.

We selected five individuals who had a degree or diploma related to Computer Science, aged between 30 and 35, who were native Sri Lankans and fluent in Sinhala, to gather data by collecting images containing both textual and visual components. They were provided with several examples, and our requirements were clearly explained to them. Where necessary, the Bulk Image Downloader tool [52] was utilized to download multiple images at once. We analyzed the posts and identified common keywords that frequently appear in violent posts. We investigated the image posts on social media to identify violent image posts and potential violent key words used in the text of these posts. To locate violent image posts, the identified violent keywords such as "මුස්ලිමානුව" (another term for Muslims), "හමිබය" (another term for Muslims), "මුස්ලිම්" (Muslim), "තෝ" (you), "මරනවා" (kill), and "පලයන්" (run away) were employed. However, this keyword driven method may not capture the entire spectrum of violent content, as it primarily relies on the presence of predefined terms. To mitigate this issue, in addition to using specific keywords, we also collected posts from pages dedicated to sexism and from other pages that often include sarcastic or implicit expressions. For non-violent posts, we collected data from pages related to topics such as love, knowledge, parenting techniques, cricket, quotes, and religion. Overall, the

data collection process spanned four months, during which a total of 6,400 posts were collected.

3.2.2 Data Filtering

During the data filtering process, the first task was to remove duplicate posts and those containing only visual or textual components. However, due to limitations in the OCR based text extraction process, we manually reviewed each image post and removed those with low resolution, complex backgrounds, and images containing non-Unicode fonts. This filtering process makes the dataset cleaner than typical "wild" social media data. However, the cleaning process can be a limitation for generalizability, yet it serves as an essential part for initial multimodal architecture creation. After completion of this process, a total of 5,600 image posts were retained. Although the dataset creation is a significant effort for a low resource language like Sinhala, the dataset size might not be sufficient for complex deep learning models, when compared with languages such as English.

3.2.3 Data Annotation

In the annotation process, two annotators were involved. They were instructed to consider both textual and visual elements when assigning labels to posts. If either the text or the visual content was violent, the post was labeled as violent. Violent posts included those that depicted discrimination based on differing beliefs, emotional harm caused by discrimination, or sexism. Furthermore, violence on digital platforms is not always overt or physical. Sarcasm, which is a form of passive aggression, can inflict psychological harm which can perpetuate emotional violence which in return creates physical violence. Therefore, posts containing humor were also considered violent if they had the potential to cause emotional harm. However, the binary categorization, which we have introduced as a baseline model may not capture the subjectivity involved in interpreting emotional or humorous violence. Therefore, we have suggested a granular or multi-label annotation in the conclusion and future scope section.

Following the same guidelines, the text and visual parts were also annotated separately. To assess agreement between the two annotators, Cohen's kappa [53] was calculated using the scikit-learn library. Cohen's kappa value for the dataset was 0.8, indicating substantial agreement. Similarly, the

kappa value for both the text and visual components was also found to be 0.8. After dataset annotation, the final dataset consisted of 3,600 non-violent and 2,000 violent image posts.

3.2.4 Final Dataset Overview

However, due to scarcity of violent images, the final dataset consists of 2,000 non-violent and 2,000 violent images. Data distribution is illustrated in Figure 2. Figures 3 and 4 illustrate examples of non-violent and violent images, respectively.

Figure 2. Data Distribution

Figure 3: A non-violent image post

Figure 4: A violent image post

3.3 Text Extraction

3.3.1 Manual Extraction

Text extraction was a challenging step. Initially, we manually extracted the text from the image posts and stored them in an Excel sheet. This extracted text was then used for training and validating the ML models.

3.3.2 OCR-based Extraction

In the next step, we employed Tesseract [45], an open-source OCR tool, for automatic text extraction. According to previous studies, relying on pre-extracted text can overestimate the performance of models. Therefore, using OCR to extract the text from the original posts and validating the ML models is a crucial step in our research. Although OCR-based extraction is a challenging step in the context of Sinhala language, this foundational work is a contribution to the research community in Sri Lanka. However, OCR-based extraction limitations can affect the result, this initial work can be improved in the future for more accurate outputs.

3.3.3 Pre-processing Techniques in OCR-based Extraction

Although Tesseract is trained in the Sinhala language, we could not use it directly on our dataset due to the informal nature of the text, variability in text placement, different fonts, and varying text sizes. The Image posts contain diverse fonts, orientations, and backgrounds, making it necessary to apply various pre-processing techniques for each case. We utilized the OpenCV Python library for image processing. After exploring several approaches, we selected the bilateral filter [45] along with different binary threshold levels for pre-processing. The bilateral filter is a non-linear filter that preserves edges, reduces noise, and smooths the image.

3.3.4 Font Training in Tesseract

Tesseract OCR was chosen for its support of the Sinhala language, particularly its ability to identify standard Unicode (UN) fonts without complex formatting and backgrounds. Since social media image posts often feature various fonts, we identified some of these fonts and proceeded to train Tesseract accordingly. Each font was trained for 7,000 to 10,000 epochs using Google Colab. Notably,

the Sinhala fonts “UN Derana”, “UN Abhaya”, “UN Sandhyanee”, “UN Basuru”, “UN Ganganee”, and “UN Rashmi” [36] were integrated into Tesseract’s training data files, located in the “tesdata” folder.

To train new fonts, we required the “.traineddata” and “.lstm” models specifically designed for the Sinhala language. The “.traineddata” file in Tesseract is essential for text recognition, as it contains character sets, word lists, and other data necessary for Tesseract to recognize text in a particular language, along with the “.lstm” model. These pre-trained models can handle a wide variety of fonts and text styles. We obtained the “.traineddata” file from “tesdata_best” [54], which hosts the best models available on the Tesseract website. Next, we extracted the “.lstm” model from the “.traineddata” file using the provided commands in Tesseract.

To train Tesseract, ground truth data is required. Tesseract provides a text file for each language, which is used to create a tiff image file along with a box file that contains details about the characters in the tiff file. These necessary files, including the text file, can be found in the “langdata_lstm” [55], which is available for download from the Tesseract website. The “lstmtraining” command-line option is used to train Tesseract for a specific font, and for this process, the tiff/box files, “.traineddata”, and “.lstm” files specific to the Sinhala language were provided.

Subsequently, we selected 200 images from the original training dataset and applied a bilateral filter to reduce noise. We then employed binary thresholding to optimize text legibility, experimenting with various threshold levels for each image. The resulting outputs, based on different threshold levels for each image, were collected in an array and sent to Tesseract. This process generated distinct Tesseract output texts, each linked to a specific threshold. The text extracted from Tesseract was then further processed to obtain the final output. We evaluated the OCR based text extraction with the test dataset and output achieved is described in the results section.

3.3.5 Post-processing and Error Correction in OCR-based Extraction

A customized post-processing module was employed to minimize errors generated by Tesseract. English words, special characters, punctuation, numbers, and spaces at the beginning and end of

sentences were removed. In some cases, Tesseract produced empty outputs for certain threshold levels, and these instances were excluded. A dictionary of Sinhala words was sourced from the Tesseract repository. Each output obtained at different threshold levels was validated against this dictionary. Every word in each output, across varying threshold levels, was assessed against the dictionary. The sentence containing the highest number of words from the dictionary was selected as the final extracted text. Subsequently, each word in the chosen sentence was checked for errors. Certain characters were produced differently in Tesseract, and we rectified typical character errors.

3.3.6 Accuracy Evaluation in OCR-based Extraction

We introduced a technique for assessing text accuracy by measuring the correspondence between the text obtained through OCR and manually extracted text. We introduced this custom evaluation because the primary objective of this research is to ensure that all the words in the original text is present in the extracted text, rather than achieving perfect character-level or word-level accuracy. This comparison is conducted at the word level, considering instances where a word may appear multiple times. To evaluate our model, we selected a subset of the training dataset that includes trained fonts and images without complex backgrounds.

We developed an algorithm, illustrated in Algorithm 1, to compare two sentences and evaluate the similarity between manually extracted text and automatically extracted text. For sentences to be considered similar, all words in the manually extracted text must be present in the automatically extracted text, maintaining the same word order, as extraction occurs sequentially. To assess similarity, each word in the manually extracted sentence is compared against the automatically extracted text.

In the algorithm 1, Sentence1 represents the manually extracted text, and Sentence2 represents the automatically extracted text. First, consecutive spaces in the manually extracted text are removed. The text is then split by spaces to create a set of unique words. Similarly, the automatically extracted text is split by spaces.

For each unique word in Sentence1, the occurrence of that word is counted in both Sentence1

(as count1) and Sentence2 (as count2). If the word count for a specific word in the automatically generated sentence (Sentence2) exceeds that in the original sentence (Sentence1), count1 is used. Otherwise, count2 is taken as the word count. The counts for all words are then aggregated and divided by the total word count of the manually extracted sentence to determine the accuracy of the generated text.

3.4 Visual Extraction

After text extraction, our next objective was to extract the visual components from image posts.

3.4.1 Text Region Detection

We used Tesseract bounding boxes and the EAST [56] text detection algorithm to identify text regions within the images. The areas defined by the bounding boxes were saved as individual image files in a designated folder.

3.4.2 Mask Creation and Text Isolation

Next, we created an empty mask with dimensions matching those of the original image to delineate the regions occupied by text. By computing the difference between the mask and the original image, we successfully isolated the visual elements of the original image. However, we acknowledge that inaccuracies in the text detection phase can lead to inaccuracies in visual-only extraction as well as classification.

3.5 Text Classification

After extracting the textual and visual components, the next step is classification. Before classifying the text, it is essential to perform cleaning and pre-processing. This section details the text cleaning and pre-processing techniques, along with the DL models used for the text classification task. Furthermore, our hyperparameter tuning was twofold, where GridSearch was applied to comparatively smaller models such as CNN, while manual fine-tuning was applied to complex models such as XLM-R due to computational constraints. However, manual fine-tuning in XLM-R can hinder further performance gain, which we intend to do in the future by accessing more computation resources.

3.5.1 Text Cleaning and pre-processing

Text cleaning is the process of removing noise and other undesirable content in text and transforming the text into a suitable format for analysis. The first step in text cleaning is Pali text removal. Pali text refers to ancient canonical scriptures in Theravada Buddhism. Some of the image posts related to Buddhism contain Pali text, which is not relevant to our classification task. Therefore, we identified and removed such text from the dataset. The next step is modifying incorrect white spaces. In formal writing, a punctuation mark is typically followed by a white space. However, in the text within our dataset, this convention was not consistently followed. To standardize spacing, we employed regular expressions to detect and correct instances where punctuation marks were incorrectly placed without space or excessive spacing. In the Sinhala alphabet, certain letters produce the same sound but are not interchangeable according to grammatical rules. However, in informal writing, these letters are often used interchangeably, including in image posts. We specifically identified two pairs of letters, ඡ and ජ, as well as ජ and ජ, which are frequently used in this manner. To address this, we replaced all such instances with one standardized format. In addition, punctuation marks and numbers were removed from the text.

After cleaning the text, the next step is text pre-processing, which involves further transformations to make the text suitable for ML models. Splitting text into words is a crucial step in pre-processing. We have splitted the text from white spaces employing "word_tokenize" in the natural language toolkit (NLTK) and "SinhalaTokenizer" from "sinling" [38].

Additionally, we eliminated stop words that are commonly used in the Sinhala language, such as ඒ, මේ, නමී, ඇති, එක, කර, හා, නෑ, වන, වූ, ද, බව, ගැන, කරයි, අතර, යන, ලෙස, නිසා, which correspond to "that, this, if, has, it, do, and, not, becoming, became, or, fact, about, does, between, going, as, because" in English. We also removed stem words such as මම, මට, මටම, මටත්, මගේ, මගේම, මාගේ, මාගෙ, මාව, මාවම, අපි, අපිම, අපිවම, අපට, අපටම, අපව, අපවම, අපේ, අපේම, which translate to "I, to me, to me myself, to me too, my, my own, my, my, me, myself, we, we ourselves, us ourselves, to us, to us ourselves, us, us ourselves, our, our own" in English.

Subsequently, we split the text dataset into training, validation, and test sets using an 8:1:1 ratio. We utilized Python's scikit-learn library [57] for dataset splitting.

3.5.2 Text padding and vocabulary creation

Initially, a vocabulary was created by including all tokens from the training set, and each token was assigned a unique ID. The maximum sentence length was determined based on the longest sentence in terms of tokens. Sentences were then padded with special tokens to match this length. The same vocabulary was applied to the validation set, and any unseen tokens were replaced with an unknown token.

3.5.3 Feature engineering

Feature engineering is the process of selecting and transforming features from raw data to improve the performance of ML models. For this purpose, we utilized word2vec [58] as an embedding mechanism. Word2vec is a shallow neural network trained to predict context words that have two variations: Continuous bag-of-words (CBOW) and skip-gram. We explored the word2vec approach: using pre-trained models [37], [59] and training a custom model on our dataset. In order to train a model, we combined our training dataset with an existing Sinhala text dataset [37], [60]. However, the performance of the custom trained models was low, leading us to continue experiments using pre-trained models.

3.5.4 Classification Algorithms

We employed various classification algorithms, including 1D CNN [61], LSTM [62], and GRU [63] models. Additionally, we utilized ensemble models by combining 1D CNN with LSTM, GRU, and BiGRU [64] to enhance performance.

In 1D CNN, three filters with sizes 3,4, and 5 were applied in parallel to the input text. The Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU) activation function was then applied to all three outputs. A max pooling operation followed to extract the most prominent features, after which a concatenation operation combined the outputs from the three filters. The concatenated output was then passed through a fully connected layer to produce the final binary classification: violent or non-violent. Figure 5 depicts the architecture of the 1D CNN model. In the

LSTM and GRU models, the number of layers and the size of the hidden layer were adjusted to optimize performance. In the ensemble model, 1D CNN output, after concatenation, is passed to the GRU or LSTM models. The output from these models is then processed through a fully connected layer to generate the final classification. Figure 6 illustrates the architecture of the CNN and GRU ensemble model.

3.5.5 Hyperparameter tuning with GridSearch

A customized “GridSearch” approach was employed to identify the optimal parameter combination to achieve the highest accuracy in CNN, LSTM, and GRU-based models. The parameters considered for tuning included the learning rate, number of epochs, and optimizer. The algorithm 2, outlines the customized “GridSearch” method used for deep learning algorithms with natural language processing. The inputs for the “GridSearch” algorithm are text data and labels, while the output is the set of hyperparameter values that yield the highest model performance. The process begins by defining a wrapper class with instance variables for the vocabulary and maximum text length. In the fit method, training data is tokenized and converted to token IDs, with the vocabulary and maximum length stored. Pre-trained embeddings are used to initialize the deep learning model, and a data loader is created for the embedded dataset to train the model. The predict method tokenizes the validation dataset using the vocabulary and length parameters obtained from the training, generated token IDs, and predicts labels. A grid of hyperparameters is defined, along with a stratified data-splitting mechanism to ensure class balance. We utilized “GridSearchCV” from the scikit-learn library [57], along with a wrapper model, a parameter grid, an accuracy metric, and stratified sampling. The “GridSearch” fits the data across all parameter combinations to determine and return the best-performing hyperparameters. For the learning rate, we used values of 0.1, 0.01, 0.001. For optimization, we experimented with Adadelta[65] [66], RMSprop [65], Adam [67], and SGD [68]. The number of epochs was set to 10, 100, 200, 300, and 400 during the training process.

3.5.6 Text Classification using XLM-R Model

Furthermore, we fine-tuned a transformer-based pre-trained model, XLM-R, specifically for our dataset to leverage its ability to handle multilingual text effectively. XLM-R [69] is a transformer-based model pre-trained in 100 different languages in an

unsupervised manner. In our approach, we utilized a pre-trained XLM-R model from the Hugging Face library [70]. The process begins with sentence splitting, followed by subword tokenization. In XLM-R, words are split into subwords, where words are broken down into smaller units, like prefixes and suffixes. This allows the model to handle out-of-vocabulary words by constructing them from known subwords, making its vocabulary a mix of full words and subwords. Each subword is assigned to a token ID. Special token, such as <s> and <_s>, are included to mark the beginning and end of sequences, respectively. Additionally, padded tokens are added at the end of sequences if they are shorter than the maximum length. An attention mask is created to distinguish between actual tokens and padded tokens. The tokenized sequence is then transformed into embeddings, with positional encoding applied to indicate the position of each token in the sequence. Finally, the tokenized, embedded, and encoded sequence is fed into the model. For our research, we utilized the “XLMRobertaTokenizer” for tokenization and “XLMRobertaForSequenceClassification” as the model.

3.6 Visual Classification

For the classification of image components, we employed several pre-trained image classification models, including AlexNet [71], MobileNet [72], ResNet [73], GoogLeNet [74], Vision Transformers (ViT) [75], and EfficientNet [76]. These models were chosen because of their effectiveness in feature extraction and classification tasks in diverse image datasets.

3.7 Multimodal Classification

After training the textual and visual components of image posts separately, our next objective was to integrate these models and develop a multimodal model for classifying image posts. In this study, we employed a late fusion approach as this is the first attempt to use data fusion for the detection of violence in Sinhala. However, we have described other fusion methods that can be used in the conclusion and future scope section. We employed a multimodal model that integrates textual and visual components through a weighted average mechanism to produce the result. As shown in Figure 7, the process begins by inserting an image into the model. Tesseract OCR is used to extract text from the image. Subsequently,

text regions are identified using Tesseract bounding boxes and the EAST algorithm, enabling the isolation of visual components.

The extracted text is pre-processed and directed to the text classification model, while the extracted visual components are sent to the image classification model. The outputs from both models are combined into a vector format, which is then fed into a ML model. Specifically, SVM, Naive Bayes (NB), and Logistic Regression (LR) models were employed. Figure 7 depicts multimodal model architecture. We have trained the ML models using our training and validation datasets and tested with the testing dataset.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section includes the results obtained for text classification, visual classification, and multimodal classification.

4.1 Results for text classification

First, we used “GridSearch” to identify the best hyperparameter combination for each deep learning model. For the evaluation, accuracy was utilized. According to Table 2, 1D CNN has obtained higher accuracy with learning rate of 0.001, 10 epochs, and RMSprop optimization for the validation dataset. The Ensemble model combining 1D CNN with GRU also achieved higher accuracy. Due to the requirement of extensive resources, we were unable to use “GridSearch” for the XLM-R model. However, by manually fine-tuning the parameters, we were able to obtain the results in Table 3 for the validation dataset. The loss plot and accuracy plot of XLM-R for the training and validation datasets are depicted in Figures 8 and 9 respectively.

Figure 8: Training and validation dataset Loss Plots

Figure 9: Training and validation dataset Accuracy Plots

Furthermore, we compared the XLM-R and 1D CNN models using the test dataset. According to the results in Table 4, XLM-R has outperformed 1D CNN.

Table 4: The XLM-R and 1D CNN results comparison on test dataset

Model	Accuracy	Precision	F Score	Recall
XLM-R	0.9287	0.9239	0.9077	0.8922
1D CNN	0.8775	0.8858	0.8768	0.8775

4.2 Results for visual classification

We utilized pre-trained models for visual classification as described in the Materials and Methods section. Subsequently, we executed all models for 100 epochs with a learning rate of 0.0001, utilizing the Adam optimizer. The results are presented in Table 5. As shown in Table 5, ResNet outperformed all other models in the test dataset.

4.3 Results for multimodal classification

For multimodal classification, XLM-R was employed as the text classification model, while ResNet was used for visual classification. These models were selected based on their superior performance compared to the other models evaluated. The results of the test set are presented in Table 6 and Figure 10.

According to the results, the multimodal model has outperformed other unimodal models.

5 SIGNIFICANCE OF THE PROPOSED APPROACH

According to the literature reviewed, violence detection has predominantly focused on English, which is considered a high-resource language. Text-based violence detection is more prominent, whereas other modalities have been explored less extensively. Very few datasets include both text and images, and for Sinhala—a low-resource language—no such datasets have been identified. Our study addresses this gap by introducing a balanced Sinhala multimodal dataset and developing a hybrid model that combines textual and visual features. These contributions collectively position our work as a significant advancement in low-resource multimodal violence detection.

6 CONCLUSION AND FUTURE SCOPE

The primary objective of this research is to classify Sinhala image posts as violent or non-violent. To achieve this, the first step was to obtain a suitable dataset. As an additional objective, a new balanced Sinhala image post dataset was curated to address this requirement. The dataset comprises both textual and visual components of each post, provided separately. By introducing this newly curated, balanced dataset containing both text and image components, we successfully addressed the data scarcity challenge for low-resource Sinhala content.

The subsequent objectives include the extraction and classification of textual and visual components. We utilized Tesseract OCR for text extraction and deep learning (DL) models for classification.

We trained and evaluated standard DL models and fine-tuned a pre-trained XLM-R model for textual classification, which demonstrated higher accuracy. For visual classification, pre-trained models were employed. Furthermore, we introduced a late fusion multimodal model for Sinhala image post classification, achieving an accuracy of 95% and outperforming the unimodal models. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first attempt in Sri Lanka to apply multimodal classification techniques to social media content.

We have classified these posts as either violent or non-violent; however, future studies can expand this classification into more nuanced categories such as overt violence, covert violence, and non-violence. Furthermore, we recognized the need to explore more categories of violence such as emotional, physical, symbolic, and ideological violence to extend our dataset. Although this study employed a late fusion technique, future research can explore the effectiveness of alternative fusion strategies. Additionally, the use of pre-trained multimodal models such as MMBT, ViLBERT, and other emerging transformer-based architectures can be investigated to enhance classification performance and to enable comparative analysis with the results of this study.

All core objectives were fully met, with significant improvement observed in multimodal classification performance. However, due to OCR limitations in extracting low-quality text, the textual feature extraction objective was partially constrained, suggesting avenues for future improvement. We also faced challenges in collecting violent images, as they were scarce. As a solution to the OCR problem, we suggest experimenting with transformer-based OCR models to achieve better results. Furthermore, we recommend using Contrastive Language–Image Pretraining (CLIP) or Multilingual CLIP (M-CLIP) with Sinhala prompt-based classification, which can potentially eliminate the need for OCR altogether. To collect more violent posts, we suggest incorporating a broader range of violent keywords in the search process. This approach is expected to help increase the number of samples in the violent category of our dataset.

In summary, the study not only achieved its objectives but also made a valuable contribution to the field of violence detection in low-resource languages by providing a robust dataset and demonstrating the efficacy of multimodal fusion techniques.

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Table 1. Taxonomy of Related Work in Violence Detection Research

Year and reference	Title	Techniques	Summary
[8]	Smokey: Automatic Recognition of Hostile Messages	Natural language processor, a rule-based parser, decision tree-based approach	The system was able to classify 98% of 'okay' and 64% of 'flame' correctly. Limitations in the study were difficulties in classifying sarcasm, complex sentences, and sentences with mistakes in grammar, punctuation etc.
[9]	Detecting Flames and Insults in Text	Rule-based parser	Limitation in the approach is words should be in the lexicon entry to be identified as hate.
[10]	Hateful Symbols or Hateful People? Predictive Features for Hate Speech Detection on Twitter	character n-grams with LR	This method has yielded superior results compared to word n-grams.
[11]	Automated Hate Speech Detection and the Problem of Offensive Language	Unigrams, bigrams, trigrams weighted with TF-IDF, LR, linear SVM, NB, DT, and RF	The results showed that LR and linear SVM performed better than the other three algorithms. L2 regularization combined with LR improved the accuracy of the normal linear regression model.
[77]	Detecting Hate Speech in Social Media	Character n-grams, word n-grams, skip-grams, and SVM	Used the Davidson et al. dataset to detect hate speech in tweets. The Character 4-gram method has shown better results than other methods
[13]	Detecting Hate Speech and Offensive Language on Twitter Using Machine Learning: An n-gram and TF-IDF Based Approach	NB, LR, and SVM with TF-IDF weighted n-gram features with L2 regularization and L1 regularization	NB and LR achieved comparable results with L2 regularization. Furthermore, Gaydhani et al. found the results can be further improved with TF-IDF weighted n-gram features.
[15]	Automatic Hate Speech Detection using Machine Learning: A Comparative Study	Bigram with TF-IDF, word2vec, and doc2vec as features and LR, NB, RF, SVM, k-NN, DT, AdaBoost, and Multilayer Perceptron (MLP)	Found higher results using SVM with bigram than other feature extraction methods for tweet sentiment analysis
[16]	Deep Learning for Hate Speech Detection in Tweets	CNN, LSTM, and fastText with random embedding or GloVe. SVM, LR, and GBDT with Char n-gram, TF-IDF and BoW	DNN achieved better results than shallow machine learning methods. Higher results were obtained by utilizing random embeddings trained with LSTM and using them in a GBDT algorithm for classification.
[17]	Using Convolutional Neural Networks to Classify Hate-Speech	CNN with four feature extraction methods such as random vectors, word2vec, character n-grams, and a combination of word2vec with character n-grams	The random embedding-based CNN approach has demonstrated superior results compared to the baseline method proposed by Waseem and Hovy
[18]	One-step and Two-step Classification for Abusive Language Detection on Twitter	LR, SVM, fastText, charCNN, wordCNN, and hybridCNN	HybridCNN with LR showed superior performance compared to other methods

[19]	Detecting Hate Speech on Twitter Using a Convolution-GRU Based Deep Neural Network	CNN and GRU	The authors have created a dataset related to the refugees and Muslims discussion in Twitter. The method has surpassed SVM based methods for the dataset created in this study. This method has surpassed the results of the study that utilized LSTM and GBDT conducted by Badjatiya et al. for the dataset created by Davidson et al.
[20]	Hate Speech Detection: A Solved Problem? The Challenging Case of Long Tail on Twitter	CNN and GRU	The new method has surpassed state-of-the-art methods on Twitter datasets utilizing SVM based method proposed by Davidson et al. with unigram, bigram, and trigram with TF-IDF and PoS
[21]	A BERT-Based Transfer Learning Approach for Hate Speech Detection in Online Social Media	BERT, BiLSTM, and CNN.	BERT-based method has produced better results than other state-of-the-art methods such as character n-gram with LR [10], [11]
[22]	Deep Learning for Hate Speech Detection: A Comparative Study	TF-IDF, the pretrained GloVe embedding of tweets, or transformers-based embedding. SVM, XGB and MLP. CNN or BiLSTM. BERT, Small BERT, ALBERT, and ELECTRA.	Transformer based methods outperform shallow learning-based methods. The TF-IDF-based shallow ML classifier outperforms other Glove – enabled DL models for most of the datasets.
[23]	BERT-based Ensemble Learning for Multi-aspect Hate Speech Detection	BERT based	The proposed model was compared with pooled stacked Bi-LSTM, BiGRU models and ensemble models that combine the outputs of BERT, BiLSTM, and BiGRU. In terms of AUC score, the pretrained BERT-based model exhibited better performance than other deep learning models.
[28]	Identifying Aggression and Toxicity in Comments using Capsule Network	Capsule network with Focal Loss	The proposed capsule network has outperformed the methods involved LSTM and CNN architectures.
[30]	Identifying Racist Social Media Comments in Sinhala Language Using Text Analytics Models with Machine Learning	SVM and n-gram approach using TF-IDF as the weighting function	The model's performance exhibited a decline with the expansion of the dataset size.
[33]	Identification of Hate Speech in Social Media	BoW, TF-IDF, and BoF. NB, SVM, LR, DT, and k-means clustering	NB with TF-IDF achieved a better F-score than other methods. Supervised models performed better than unsupervised models.
[31]	Identification of Abusive Sinhala Comments in Social Media using Text Mining and Machine Learning Techniques	BoW, word n-gram, character n-gram, word skip-gram. SVM, MNB, and RFDT	MNB showed better results than other classifiers. Character trigram and character four-gram showed better results than other feature extraction methods.

[32]	Machine Learning-Based Automated Tool to Detect Sinhala Hate Speech in Images	Shallow ML techniques.	MNB has shown better precision, recall, and F-measure than other ML techniques.
[33]	Identification of Hate Speech in Social Media	BoW, TF-IDF, and BoF. NB, SVM, LR, DT, and k-means clustering	NB with TF-IDF achieved a better F-score than other methods. Supervised models performed better than unsupervised models.
[34]	Adapter Based Fine-Tuning of Pretrained Multilingual Language Models for Code-Mixed and Code-Switched Text Classification	XLM-R	Outperformed all other models including capsule network proposed by [37], LSTM, and BiLSTM networks. XLM-R with adapters has further improved the results.
[35]	BERTifying Sinhala -- A Comprehensive Analysis of Pretrained Language Models for Sinhala Text Classification	XLM-R, LaBSE, and LASER	XLM-R has performed better than other models.
[37]	Sentiment Analysis for Sinhala Language using Deep Learning Techniques	word2vec and fastText. LSTM, RNN, GRU, BiLSTM, ensemble models such as CNN and LSTM, stacked models such as stacked LSTM, and capsule models.	Capsule models demonstrated superior performance compared to other methods.
[38]	Protest Activity Detection and Perceived Violence Estimation from Social Media Images	CNN and OpenFace-based model [79]	While their model excelled at identifying violent scenes, it did not perform well in emotion detection.
[39]	Multi-view Learning for Visual Violence Recognition with Maximum Entropy Discrimination and Deep Features	Multi-View Maximum Cross Entropy Discrimination	The proposed method experimented with an arbitrary number of views, demonstrating superior performance compared to single-view and multi-view methods employing CNN, SVM, KNN, LR, and NB.
[40]	Multimodal Social Media Analysis for Gang Violence Prevention	Unigram, bigram, Part-of-Speech (POS), and CNN features, R-CNN, Inceptionv3. Early fusion and late fusion were used as multi-modal feature extraction methods. SVM as the classification algorithm.	Multimodal methods outperformed text-only or image-only methods.
[42]	Multimodal Meme Dataset (MultiOFF) for Identifying Offensive Content in Image and Text	stacked LSTM, BiLSTM and CNN for text features. VGG-16 for image features.	Results demonstrated that the multi-modal approach has outperformed methods that incorporate only a single mode
[43]	The Hateful Memes Challenge: Detecting Hate Speech in Multimodal Memes	ResNet, Faster-RCNN, and BERT	The multimodal approach using early fusion yielded superior results.
[44]	Memes in the Wild: Assessing the Generalizability of the	BERT, ResNet, VGG-19 and DenseNet.	The approaches using pretrained multimodal models yielded superior results.

Hateful Memes
Challenge Dataset

Multimodal pretrained
models include MMBT,
ViLBER.

Figure 1: Process of textual and visual classification of an image post

Figure 5: 1D CNN model

Figure 6: 1D CNN and GRU ensemble model

Figure 7: Multimodal model

Table 2: The GridSearch results of different models

Model	Learning rate	Number of epochs	Optimization algorithm	Accuracy
1D CNN + BiGRU	0.01	10	Adam	0.89768
1D CNN	0.001	10	RMSprop	0.9184
1D CNN + GRU	0.01	200	SGD	0.90143
1D CNN + LSTM	0.001	100	Adam	0.89104
LSTM	0.001	100	Adam	0.72738

Table 3: The XLM-R results

Model	Learning rate	Number of epochs	Optimization algorithm	Accuracy
XLM-R	0.000001	400	AdamW	0.92

Table 6: Comparative Analysis of Accuracy in Unimodal and Multimodal Models

Text Classification Accuracy	Visual Classification Accuracy	Multimodal Accuracy	OCR Accuracy
92.87	88.94	95.18	78.64

Figure 10: Comparative Performance Analysis of Different Modalities

Algorithm 1: Calculate Word Level Accuracy of a Sentence

- 1: Input: sentence1, sentence2
- 2: Replace multiple spaces in sentence1 with a single space
- 3: Split the sentence1 from spaces
- 4: Set wordsSent1 to the output from the splitted sentence1
- 5: Creates a set containing the unique elements from the list wordsSent1 → wordsSent1Unique
- 6: Set totalWords to length of wordsSent1
- 7: Replace ZERO WIDTH NON-JOINER character in sentence2
- 8: Split the sentence2 from spaces
- 9: Set wordsSent2 to the output from the splitted sentence2
- 10: Set count zero
- 11: if empty words in wordsSent1Unique then
- 12: Remove empty words from wordsSent1Unique
- 13: end if
- 14: for word in wordsSent1Unique do
- 15: Set count1 to the number of occurrences of word in wordsSent1
- 16: Set count2 to the number of occurrences of word in wordsSent2
- 17: if count1 < count2 then
- 18: Set count to count + count1
- 19: else
- 20: Set count to count + count2
- 21: end if
- 22: end for
- 23: Set accuracy = (count / totalWords) × 100
- 24: return accuracy

Algorithm 2: GridSearch method

- 1: **Input:** text, labels
- 2: **Output:** best performing hyperparameter values
- 3: Define a wrapper class
- 4: Declare instance variables, to store the vocabulary and maximum length of the text corpus
- 5: Fit method: input X and Y (training text and labels)
- 6: Tokenize the text
- 7: Encode tokens to ids. In the tokenization process, the generated vocabulary and maximum length of the text are saved to variables
- 8: Load pre-trained embeddings and send them to the deep learning model to initialize the model
- 9: Create a dataloader for the embedded dataset
- 10: Train the model
- 11: Predict method: input testing text dataset
- 12: Tokenize the testing text dataset
- 13: Use the vocabulary and maximum length generated in the training process
- 14: Create the ids for the test text dataset
- 15: Predict the labels
- 16: Define the parameter grid
- 17: Define the dataset splitting mechanism: stratified split
- 18: GridSearchCV in scikit learn is called with the wrapper model, parameter grid, scoring mechanism as accuracy or any other metric, and dataset splitting mechanism as stratified or any other sampling mechanism
- 19: Then the GridSearch can be fitted to our data and retrieve the best performing hyperparameter values
